

Suggestions for the Improvement of China-Korea Relations under the Dire State of China-Korea Relations: An Analysis of the Proposal based on the Possibility of Future Development in the Field of Sino-Korean Diplomacy

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Abstract: China and South Korea share a close, irreplaceable, and interconnected relationship, whether it be through thousands of years of history, close geographic ties, or the common influence of Confucianism, whether it be at the top of the government or among the people. In recent years, with the world in turmoil and the emergence of various factions and interest groups, it seems to be a critical moment for researchers and learners in the field of international disciplines to explore the relationship between China and South Korea. This paper is based on the diplomacy of China and South Korea, with the possibility of future development of the two countries at the diplomatic level as the core element, and the suggestion that China and South Korea can improve their relationship through diplomacy in the future will be the focus of this paper. Compared with the existing research, this paper does not reflect too much theoretical research, but focuses on practical research on the solution of real problems, which is also a key difference between this paper and other existing research. This paper is written with the hope of presenting the readers with some of the problems that we are facing in our time, and also to draw their attention to the future development of the relationship between China and South Korea. In this way, the significance of this paper is not lost.

Keywords: China-Korea Diplomacy, China-Korea Relations, Future Development, International Dynamics, Proposals for Solving Social Problems.

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1 Introduction

The vein of state-to-state relations is not a product of modern society, but has been reflected in the development of past history for thousands of years. In today's society, when we talk about state-to-state relations, what are we focusing on more than anything else? Did representatives of both governments go on a trip? Did they sign an agreement? Was there a co-operation? Did they produce concrete and public results? Admittedly, these topics are real and are an important indication of the state of communication between the two countries. But in today's highly volatile societies, what we see and what we chase is fraught with countless uncertainties. For example, the Chinese proverb, "the order was changed in the morning, the order was changed in the evening", is actually an illustration of the instability of policies or the fickleness of those in power.

A dissertation is not a simple output of words, nor is it a simple summary of descriptions. It is true that in today's Chinese society, many scholars have suffered from political dissertation censorship, and have been bound into all kinds of restrictive environments where they are not allowed to

write, not allowed to publish, and not allowed to research. However, the author has always believed that a dissertation is more of a scholar's analysis of the problems that have already occurred in the world under study, or a scholar's prognosis of the possibilities of future world development, and from this academic point of view, a dissertation is in fact more like a tool used by scholars to express themselves. This is just like the actors acting, singers singing, and hosts hosting programmes in film and television. Although there are many scholars nowadays who are far away from the morality of academics itself, the essential morality of academics will not be altered no matter how the world changes and how the Other acts. In the author's opinion, the greatest meaning of existence of academia is only two, one is to discover and elaborate the social problems that have occurred or are occurring, and to provide solutions for this research; the second is to make a leading role for the future development of society, and to build up the possibilities of a new world development for the people. While it is regrettable that academic research has moved away from these meanings, it is also important to understand that if we remain in this morbid inherent form of exporting dissertation works as political products on a factory

assembly line, the academic session will eventually become precarious.

Returning to the core of this article, when discussing state-to-state relations, we need to first clarify the basic concept of "diplomacy", what is diplomacy? According to Wang Zengcai's statement in Introduction to International History, we can find that the word "diplomacy" is derived from the ancient Greek word "diploma", which is composed of diplo meaning "fold in two", and ma meaning "object". "an object" [1]. It originally referred to a folded document that certified the identity of the holder, as well as the rights of passage and other rights granted. In the Roman Empire, diploma referred to documents such as passports or passes that allowed travel or transit on imperial roads [1]. In the 18th century, the French began to refer to the officials they dealt with on foreign missions as "diplomats" (French: corps diplomatique), meaning people who represented the government and engaged in negotiations [1]. It means a person who engages in negotiations on behalf of the government [1]. With the development of the relationship between countries, the connotation of "diplomacy" has also changed. According to the materials, we understand that "diplomacy" refers to the procedure or art of handling government-to-government international relations between sovereign independent states and countries on the basis of sovereign equality, which is usually conducted bilaterally and sometimes multilaterally, with negotiation and bargaining as the main means, and after the twentieth century, it was expanded to include summit meetings and other international conferences, with the aim to achieve a better understanding of the international relations between states and countries. It is usually bilateral and sometimes multilateral, with démarches and negotiations as the principal means, expanding in the twentieth century to include summits and other international conferences, with a view to reaching agreements and solving problems between States. Diplomats may also use threats or pressure when making representations, but the extent and effectiveness of these are determined by the relative power of a state or of the state making the representations[1]." From this, we can now sort out a seemingly complete traceability of the term "diplomacy", which is also the earliest definition of "diplomacy" in the academic world to date. Throughout the generations since then, diplomacy has gradually come to the forefront, especially as it applies to state-to-state exchanges or negotiations. This is the earliest trace of the term "diplomacy" and is a mode of practice that works directly in the official sphere. Given the official nature of the profession of the diplomat, who represents the interests of his country in negotiations with the interests of other countries, what are the specific purposes of diplomacy?

Similarly, we can learn from what Wang Zengcai expressed in Introduction to International History that "the purpose of diplomacy is to promote national interests. These interests are affected by geography, history and economic development, but the main priority is to safeguard the independence, integrity and security of national sovereignty

[2]. It is also important to maintain the maximum freedom of movement of the state. Again, diplomacy seeks to achieve the mission of pursuing the greatest national interests without the use of force and without arousing hatred, using language as the main method and maintaining peace as the main task. The most important function of diplomacy is to "reach agreement without violence[2]" and we know that the most important core element of diplomacy at the national level is to protect the national interest of the country or the national diplomatic interest of the country. This is also true for China, South Korea, Japan, Thailand, the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia, Canada, New Zealand, Singapore, etc. This is also the fundamental attribute of diplomacy - protecting and defending one's own national interests. And this is the part that both the countries mentioned above and those not mentioned above have done the best in terms of trade-offs in diplomatic interests. This is the first thing that the international community recognises as the key to diplomacy.

However, the problem arises from the fact that today's societies are no longer homogeneous and factionalised, and globalisation is taking shape. So, based on this reality, can we not make a hypothesis, that is, from the original single form of traditional diplomacy to the current public diplomacy, the coexistence of the two is also in the world of globalisation trend of a kind of compromise or should be born?

Returning to the focus of this paper - Sino-Korean relations, in the construction of diplomatic relations between China and South Korea today, the effect of the implementation of public diplomacy is more than the implementation of traditional diplomacy. As an example, traditional diplomacy has only one subject, the national government. The work performed by traditional diplomacy is fixed, and is used to implement the foreign policy behaviour model decided by the state. In the traditional diplomatic system, both the subject of the self and the subject of the other party are the dominant parties at the time of the two sides, and in this kind of situation, even though policy documents are signed that are very beneficial to the people of the two countries, in the actual implementation of the policy, it is often fatal to short-term timeliness. For example, let's take the example of the top levels of government in China and South Korea, from the earliest Roh Tae-woo and Jiang Zemin (Yang Shangkun), to Kim Dae-jung and Jiang Zemin, to Roh Moo-hyun and Hu Jintao, to Lee Myung-bak and Hu Jintao, to Park Geun-hye and Xi Jinping, and to Moon Jae-in and Xi Jinping. All of these demonstrated a pattern of high-level government interaction based on traditional diplomacy, but how much has it actually benefited the people of the two countries? Or how long have the people of the two countries gained a period of peace of mind as a result of high-level diplomacy between the two governments? All of this is constantly changing. It is also undeniable that every change in the leadership of the two countries mentioned above has had a significant impact on traditional diplomacy and has caused considerable

upheaval. In this case, the central governments of both countries need to rethink and change. The traditional diplomacy led by the national governments may need to allow free space for the public diplomacy that is now popular, and even provide the necessary legal and financial support, especially in the area of civil diplomacy.

Under the current circumstances, China and South Korea need to expand the space for strategic cooperation. For South Korea, strategic cooperation with China needs to maintain the flexibility of strategic choices, especially in strengthening the ROK-US alliance and maintaining the stability of ROK-China relations, and it is important to maintain the autonomy of "balanced choices". For China, strategic cooperation with South Korea also requires flexibility in strategic choices, but at the same time, China needs to gradually liberalise its inherent choices in strategic choices. Reducing differences and avoiding conflicts through consultation and coordination is not only an important guarantee for building a strategic partnership between China and South Korea, but also an important safeguard for the sustainable development of the relationship between the two countries. For the multiple and sensitive issues that already exist between the two countries, we should always insist on dialogue and communication to find consensus, and formulate concrete action plans to cool down the hot issues and control the conflict points in time, so that the relationship between the two sides will not be greatly affected. [3]

In the following section, this paper will describe these issues step by step, and in the third chapter, it will elaborate on proposals for the future development of Sino-Korean diplomacy through a combination of official and private research methods.

2 Current Social Problems

2.1 Social Problems Faced by the Chinese Civil Society

At the macro level, the social problems faced by the Chinese civil society may be more centred on the highly official Chinese news media, which have a tendency to portray the Chinese people in an unfavourable light. For example, some Chinese people call South Koreans "sticks", which is a national term of derision. For the Chinese people, who have been living in an indoctrinated environment for a long time, it may be natural for them to refer to South Korea or South Koreans without thinking about it. For Chinese people who have been living in an environment of indoctrination for a long time, when referring to South Korea or South Koreans, they may naturally say such an insulting word as "Bangzi" without thinking about it. Moreover, the logic behind this matter may not be clear to the person himself, and he may even think that this is just a nickname, just like the neighbourhood, you call me "Erdogzi" and I call you "Sanmazi". Do you think he meant

any harm? I really don't think so. After all, growing up in such an environment, it is also possible that we have formed some kind of tacit understanding between each other, that such a nickname pronouns are a sign of the relationship between the two sides of a sign of closeness. This is only true for some nationals. For foreigners, most of the time, they may not even consider these environmental and customary influences, but most likely will consider this as a kind of naked contempt or insulting behaviour, and then rise to the level of the country and the country. This is a very realistic example and a very common situation nowadays. If these only face a local, small-scale, offline kind of dissemination, in terms of the concept of the state, it may not be a big deal.

However, the problem is that these kinds of situations have already transcended geographical boundaries, and can be found everywhere on Google, Baidu, and Weibo, and it seems that vilification of other countries has become a form of nationalism or political correctness in the context of the increasingly difficult diplomatic relations between the two central governments.

2.2 Social Problems Faced by the Korean Civil Society

The social problems faced by the Korean civil society are inextricably linked to the Chinese civil society's use of nicknames and pronouns as described above. However, in addition to this, there are two other aspects of Korean civil society that the authors have in mind. One is that in recent years, as Korean universities have risen in the world's university rankings, and with the arrival of many academically excellent Chinese students, there have been more opportunities for both Koreans and Chinese to come into contact with each other, especially in the Seoul area, where Korean universities are concentrated. Although there are more opportunities for mutual contact, friction between the two parties has also increased. For example, there are differences and similarities in living habits, eating habits, and study habits. These frictions seem to have caused further friction and even tears in the news media that are now prevalent in Korea and China. Certain Chinese may feel that Koreans are overworked; certain Koreans may feel that Chinese are unhygienic; certain Chinese may feel that Koreans are impolite; certain Koreans may feel that Chinese are too condescending; and so on and so forth, and so on and so forth. It is just like an old saying: "The public say that the public is right, and the women say that the women are right". It's true that among the Koreans and Chinese that this writer has come into contact with, Koreans in general are more or less stronger than some Chinese students in terms of rubbish sorting, self-image, and commitment to homework, but these are not the whole picture, and as the Chinese folk mentioned above, what emerges and reveals itself is only a certain range of things, and does not represent the whole picture. It's like when someone asks me, what do you think of Koreans? Or what do you think of the Chinese? This is a

dead giveaway. A person is only an individual, and the world is so big that an individual has no right to represent either the Chinese or the world. Students on the same course have endless problems and diverse personality traits, so who are we as individuals to represent and judge what is good or bad for a person, let alone a member of the world we live in together? So where does the problem lie? In fact, it is that we have neglected the autonomy of generalisation, and then lost or briefly lost the ability to think independently and make rational judgements.

Secondly, with the consideration of the political orientation of the South Korean government, in recent years, the South Korean government has gradually increased the cooperation with the United States and other Western countries, for the South Korean people, from the most fundamental level of national security recognised by all the people of the community as a whole, in fact, this is the South Korean government for the threat of North Korea to carry out the attributes of a national security security of a choice. However, this point seems to sting the heart of some Chinese people, that is South Korea to China's disloyalty, and even some voices that South Korea in the United States to suppress China's future development, and therefore, further aggravate the conflict between the people of China and South Korea. In practical terms, this conflict is far more damaging than other forms of harm, such as the more obvious boycott of Korean goods, which is a threatening form of protest.

2.3 Social problems at the official level between Korea and China

Continuing on from what was said at the end of the previous section, the title of this section, while jointly outlining the official level in both Korea and China, actually has strong links to the civil level as well. For example, on the civil level in South Korea I have focused on two main points: the friction between the people of China and South Korea, represented by the Seoul area, and the political considerations of the South Korean government, which I briefly mentioned. This section will take the second point mentioned above, namely the political considerations of the Korean government, as the basic starting point for further derivation of some of the realities of the situation. Let's start with the first point, the growing relationship between South Korea and the United States. In fact, the author is not the slightest bit surprised by this point, or even expected, because in the author's view, the relationship between South Korea and the United States is only a matter of time. Why? Let's take a look at a piece of information that was gathered only after many investigations, "According to publicly available Soviet archives, Il Sung visited China several times in the early 1950's, and at a meeting on 15 May, Mao Zedong promised that China would send troops to help North Korea in the event that American troops entered the war. Mao also clarified that since the Soviet Union and the United States had agreed on the demarcation of the 38th

parallel, they could not enter the war directly, but that China had no such obligation." If this information is true, then South Korea-US relations, South Korea-China relations, or China-US relations, which have been the subject of much debate among some Chinese people in recent years, have become a cover-up in the current social context. Likewise, if this information is true, then the issues we are arguing about today have an early cause.

This principle is not really complicated to understand, for example, in the current Chinese society, in the social environment of the people's groups dominated by political correctness, what do you think will be the most mentioned content of Japan? Mount Fuji, cherry blossoms, elderly services, or the education system? None of these. In the relevant interviews and some of the data identified, the most frequent content is actually hatred. Hatred of Japan's invasion and countless killings of old China before the founding of new China. Even though so much time has passed, even though the killers of that time have died and passed away, people still feel pain and cannot let go. But in this case, we need to have a sober realisation, which is also a very obvious fact, that most of the Japanese who invaded old China in those days no longer exist, and more Japanese youths nowadays really did not grow up in those days, and did not kill the Chinese people. But why do so many Chinese people cling to this issue and do not even try to analyse the current social situation dialectically? The various issues and specific factors involved are not within the scope of this article, so I will only give a summary of them. I am not trying to prove anything by telling this example, but I just hope that we can understand that many things may not be as simple as we think. Similarly, the Sino-Korean issue that some people are disputing is also similar to this one.

For South Korea as a whole, whether it is the government or the people, there is one thing that we all know in common, and that is that the biggest threat to South Korea is always North Korea, which used to be the closest to us. In recent years, North Korean society has been constantly researching all kinds of lethal weapons, which is the most direct threat to South Korea, and may lead to the death of its citizens if it is not careful. At the same time, Russia, the former Soviet Union's successor, has been waging a war against Ukraine in recent years, and South Korea is geographically located in close proximity to Russia. These are already two destabilising factors for South Korea as a whole. Let's look at the third one, China. From the previous information, we have already seen that when North Korea first launched its war of aggression, the Chinese Communist Party's central government sided with North Korea and fought with it against South Korea at that time. In addition, in recent years, China has issued a series of official "ban on South Korea", may I ask South Korea in the face of a major national crisis, if not with the United States to make good friends with who? Whether it is Chinese scholars, Korean scholars, American scholars, or scholars from all over the world, we should look at this

matter calmly and objectively, and, correspondingly, we should do our best to make practical actions for the peaceful development of all countries in the world.

Although there are a lot of examples of civil society issues mentioned above, the focus of these issues, or the root of these issues, does not lie in the civil society, but rather in the official changes. While the Korean government's official use of civil society may be effective in South Korea, it is another level for Chinese society. In the next section, the practical solution to the problem will be briefly presented as "Why is the Chinese government unable to use civil power to improve relations between China and South Korea?" In the following section, we will also briefly summarise this point.

3 It's currently envisaged proposals for improving relations between China and South Korea

Since 1992, relations between China and the Republic of Korea have developed in a comprehensive manner and, despite a number of ups and downs, have basically maintained a cooperation-oriented tone and a stable and forward-looking overall situation. The two countries have overcome differences, contradictions and even conflicts arising from differences in political systems, strategic positioning and interest structures, and have maintained the general direction of dialogue, consultation and the pursuit of mutually beneficial cooperation. Currently, China-Korea relations are in a new period of historical transition, facing new challenges from the political, economic, socio-cultural, and values fields. [4] At present, China is both a core economic cooperation target country for South Korea and a country that can play a constructive role in resolving the North Korean nuclear issue. In the face of the complex and volatile regional situation, China and South Korea should move in the same direction and actively look for an effective way to break the deadlock and resolve issues of mutual concern. [5]

During the 30 years since the establishment of diplomatic relations between China and South Korea, the relationship between the two countries has achieved leapfrog development in various fields, including economy, politics, society and culture, with remarkable achievements. The in-depth exchanges and cooperation between the two countries have not only promoted the maximisation of the interests of the two countries, but also made important contributions to the peace, stability and prosperity of the Northeast Asian region. With the evolution of the world's political and economic landscape, changes in the geopolitical and economic environment brought about by the strategic game between China and the United States, as well as the uncertainties brought about by the new South Korean government's foreign and security policy preferences, China-South Korea relations have been subjected to a severe test. But there is no way back for China-South Korea relations. In order to build a new type of high-level China-South Korea relations for the future, the two countries need to face up to the major challenges they

are currently facing in various fields and effectively manage their differences. [6]

3.1 Political Level

Whether it is China, or Korea, or even any other country in the world, the real root of the change of problems must be closely related to politics. Socialist countries, constitutional monarchies, and democratic republics are all very different in their political systems, but the fundamental solution to most problems cannot be found in politics. This is also the question that the author did not answer in the previous chapter, namely, "Why is it impossible for Chinese officials to use civil power to improve relations between China and South Korea?"

Although China's central government is now adopting or claiming to be a socialist state, plus, although there are still a few, scattered, single-digit socialist states in the world, the model of socialist state that China's central government is actually adopting is far different from the model of social governance that other countries claiming to be socialist are adopting. At the end of the previous section, why was it said that Chinese civil power was ineffective in improving relations between China and South Korea or that even if Chinese officials were to use civil power, they would not be able to meet the expectation of improvement? In fact, it is because of China's political attributes. In the current Chinese social system, politics is above all else, and the "changing of the rules" that this article initially invoked is a common occurrence for the Chinese people today. How can the Chinese people really improve the relationship between China and South Korea in a highly centralised and unified framework of political power?

The author has always believed that South Korea is China's most solid partner, even if the two countries have established diplomatic relations for just thirty years, but both as a national government level of South Korea and China, as well as the level of the people of South Korea and the people of China, are the flesh and blood of the real existence of China and South Korea, and ask in the world of the hundreds of countries, there is no other country can be like China and South Korea such a fundamental geo-kindred relationship? The truth is that China and South Korea are not related to each other. Unfortunately, instead of becoming close partners, the two countries are now on a path of disintegration.

At the political level, there is perhaps one issue that has caused a serious dispute between China and South Korea - the issue of SAD. Both sides may have gone too far in this matter, and it is proposed that the top echelons of both governments should re-examine this issue in a calm and objective manner. Both sides must clearly understand what is the most serious problem facing the two countries that needs to be solved, and they must also clearly understand whether the future direction of the world will be one of peace and harmony, or one of disintegration. All these are firmly confined in the hands of the top echelons of

the two governments.

For this reason, at the political level of improving China-South Korea relations, this paper now makes the following generalised proposals:

- 1) The top echelons of the governments of China, South Korea and the United States should re-examine the North Korea issue and make it public;
- 2) China, South Korea, and the United States should renegotiate the SAD issue and make it public;
- 3) The United Nations should mobilise all the coalition countries to re-examine the DPRK issue and provide practical solutions, and make them public;
- 4) China and South Korea should give institutional protection to official and private exchanges in business, culture, science and technology between the two countries from the policy and legal levels, and open a green channel for the people of the two countries to exchange information, which should be made known to the public;
- 5) China and South Korea should work together to crack down on cyberbullying and malignant behaviours that undermine normal relations between the two countries and make them known to the public;
- 6) China and South Korea should reformulate policies to support the entry of foreign capital, and ensure a stable political environment for investors through stable political policy support, and make them known to the public;
- 7) The Chinese government should gradually liberalise restrictions on foreign nationals to enable them to enjoy full freedom of movement in China, and abolish unreasonable procedures for foreign nationals, and make them known to the public;

3.2 Economy

The economy is the lifeblood of a nation, and it is extremely important to China, Korea, and even to any other country in the world. However, in recent years, the economic development of China and South Korea has been in a serious decline, and both official and private economic exchanges have been affected to varying degrees. In this vicious circle, while the national level may focus more on changes in import and export trade or GDP rankings, the people of the two countries, who rely on the economic exchanges between the two countries for their survival, may be in a state of devastation.

For this reason, the author would like to make the following general proposals to improve the economic aspects of the relationship between China and South Korea:

- 1) The governments of China and South Korea should review the deficiencies of the past China-South Korea economic agreements and correct them, and make them public;
- 2) China and South Korea should re-examine the

economic development of the two countries, produce a draft cooperation bill, and make it public;

3) China and South Korea should work together to strengthen economic and trade relations with the rest of the world, sign a memorandum of co-operation, and make it public;

4) China and South Korea should work together to strengthen economic relations with the United States, the United Kingdom, the European Union, Australia, Japan, Thailand and Vietnam, and make them public;

5) The Chinese government should gradually increase the use of banking services and the opening up of the region, and gradually abolish unreasonable restrictions on foreign investors, and make them known to the public;

3.3 Cultural Dimension

The cultural dimension has always been regarded as an important manifestation of soft power diplomacy, and the cultural diplomacy strategy has indeed produced many positive effects in the past decades. However, with the further deterioration of Sino-Korean relations, the current situation of the closure of Chinese Confucius Institutes in South Korea and the restriction of Sejong Academy in South Korea is spreading, which is a great loss for the citizens of both sides. Moreover, from the functional point of view of diplomacy, cultural diplomacy is the most direct and effective means of exporting culture, which saves money and effort. Unfortunately, this has cooled down with the deterioration of Sino-Korean relations.

For this reason, this paper makes the following general proposals to improve the cultural aspect of Sino-Korean relations:

1) China and South Korea should simultaneously liberalise the restrictions on the movement of each other's nationals, reduce the procedures for cultural exchange visas or implement visa-on-arrival and visa-free policies, so as to give the people of the two countries full freedom of cultural exchanges, and to make them known to the public;

2) China and South Korea should gradually increase the exchange activities of cultural missions of the two countries, including but not limited to colleges and universities, research institutes, religious, public interest groups, social organisations, etc., and make them public;

3) China and South Korea should re-examine their respective management and operation modes in the most representative Confucius Hall and Sejong Hall, innovate the output content and output forms, strengthen the exchanges and cooperation between the two sides, and make them public;

3.4 Military

The relationship between China and South Korea in the military level may be more complex than we think,

because the author is currently mainly focused on Chinese politics and social aspects of the research and study, although occasionally involved in the military level, but it is really shallow. Therefore, I would like to put forward a general proposal to the Chinese government to strengthen the military co-operation with the South Korean government and gradually reduce the military exchanges with North Korea and Russia.

3.5 International Community

Regardless of which country is being explored, the relationship between national societies is always essential. The relationship between China and Korea seems to be the relationship between the Chinese government and the Korean government, but in fact it is also the relationship between China, Korea, and various countries in the world. Similarly, the relationship between the Chinese people and the South Korean people seems to be explored, but in fact, it is also the relationship between each country in the world and its people. The world is a circle. In the past, there may have been a world where you suffered and I was happy, but with the ecological crisis of the earth and the global change of greenhouse gases, that is no longer the case. Just like the "Butterfly Effect" that many scholars have been proposing over the years, a disaster that happens here may happen in another place the next moment. Therefore, the author would like to call on everyone in the world to take action, pay attention to China-Korea relations, and work together to promote the peaceful development of the world.

4 Conclusion

The theme of this paper is about the improvement of Sino-Korean relations under the severe state of Sino-Korean relations, under which the author divides it into the diplomatic field of China and South Korea, and tries to take the diplomatic field as the basic starting point for writing this paper, while the key part of the discussion focuses on the constructive discussion on the possibilities of future development. At present, with the surging counter-tide of unilateralism and protectionism, China and South Korea should strengthen co-operation, promote the establishment of a new pattern of an open and inclusive world economy, and facilitate the healthy development of the global economy, as well as promote communication and understanding through increased people-to-people exchanges so that the friendly relations between the two countries can be more deeply rooted in the hearts of the people of both sides. [7] In fact, both Chinese and South Korean people always have some complaints about the relationship between the two countries in recent years, which can also be seen in the online media platforms with private attributes and the news media platforms with official attributes, especially in certain news events reported by some platforms, it is not difficult to find that many netizens may not be clear about the cause of the news event or the real situation, and then start a crusade between the countries.

This is both sad and regrettable. While this situation may not cause much of a furore in the short term, in the long term, as we have mentioned in this paper about the serious relationship between China and South Korea, these may be the problematic points that cause another serious situation.

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